

NEWSLETTER

Welcome to CONCILIARE: Advancing Our Research

Welcome to the fourth edition of the CONCILIARE newsletter!

Dear colleagues, as our project progresses, we are pleased to share updates on our activities, upcoming events, and new resources. This newsletter aims to serve as a platform to promote the project's activities, parallel events, and ongoing research, keeping partners and collaborators informed and connected.

PAST EVENTS

(De)Colonial Visions

On April 28, the CONCILIARE team, in partnership with the Visual Culture Working Group of SOPCOM and the MigraMediaActs project, organized the conference “(De)Colonial Visions: Dialogues in Visual Culture, Alterities, and Artivisms”, a vibrant pre-event to the International Conference Migrations and Communication in a Planetary Age: Debates and Actions.

The program featured a guided visit entitled “Crossed Histories: Colonialism and the Paths to Decoloniality in Braga”, led by Chisoka Simões (CECS, University of Minho), followed by a roundtable discussion on “Reimagining Colonial Heritage” at the Biblioteca Lúcio Craveiro da Silva.

Seminar with Wolfgang Wagner

On May 6, Wolfgang Wagner (University of Tartu, Estonia) conducted a seminar titled “Essentialism in Intergroup Relations: Stereotyping and Fear of Mixing Essence”, in collaboration with CONCILIARE and the Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, University of Coimbra.

Symposium "Representations of the Colonial Past: Dissemination, Change and Psychosocial Impact"

On May 30, the CONCILIARE project participated in the National Symposium on Psychological Research at the University of Porto. Researchers Joaquim Pires Valentim and Rosa Cabecinhas coordinated the symposium “Representations of the Colonial Past: Dissemination, Change and Psychosocial Impact,” which featured the participation of CONCILIARE team members Felix Meuer, Emiliano Abad García, and Teresa Forte.

The session addressed the ways in which Portugal's colonial past is represented in schoolbooks, museums, political discourse, and public spaces — as well as the changes, continuities, and resistances that shape their psychosocial impact and implications for intergroup relations.

Colloque “Spoliations, restitutions et circulations des objets”

From June 4 to 6, the CONCILIARE project was represented at the international colloquium "Spoliations, restitutions et circulations des objets. Pour une géopolitique du patrimoine", organized by the journal Relations internationales in partnership with the Université de Fribourg, the Musée d'art et d'histoire, and the Muséum de Neuchâtel - based in Switzerland.

Researcher Yasmin Zian made a contribution in which she examines the key events behind Belgium's rapid change of position regarding the restitution of human remains and cultural objects. Her analysis explores the post-2022 debates on reparations and postcolonial relations with the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), shedding light on the challenges, impasses, and complexities involved in these processes.

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Deliverable 5.6 – CONCILIARE Policy Brief 1

The first CONCILIARE Policy Brief presents early-stage empirical assessments across the project's four key domains: textbooks, public spaces, museums, and the cultural consumption of products and traditions.

As this brief is released before the project's midpoint (Month 15 of 36), its recommendations are intended to outline a baseline framework of actionable principles. These will be further refined and developed as research progresses.

New Publication on Social Representations and Decolonial Challenges

The article “Memória social e desafios decoloniais: reflexões a partir de um estudo sobre representações de personalidades históricas no Brasil e em Portugal” was published in May 2025 (Vol. 59) of the Revista Interamericana de Psicología.

This collaborative work is co-authored by Luiza Lins and Rosa Cabecinhas (University of Minho, Portugal), Marcus Eugênio Oliveira Lima (Federal University of Sergipe, Brazil), Joaquim Pires Valentim (University of Coimbra, Portugal), and Elza Maria Techio (Federal University of Bahia, Brazil). The article explores social memory and decolonial challenges through the lens of how historical figures are represented in Brazil and Portugal.

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Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Júlia Vilhena, Rosa Cabecinhas, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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